

ORGANIZATION OF DIGITALIZED MEDICINE AND HEALTH ACADEMY AND ITS SIGNIFICANCE IN MEDICINE**Shermazarov Farrukh**

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Abstract. *The main goal of this academy is to promote a healthy lifestyle. It consists of covering all branches of medicine and automation of all medical directions. The main purpose of establishing a health platform is to establish a connection between people and medical professionals. It's about making all the medical services people need the way they want. The Health and Fitness Tips section contains over 5,000 health tips and health tips, all science-based, copyrighted, and sourced. All diseases are presented by sections and placed according to the source used. The origin, symptoms, causes, treatment methods of all diseases are given in detail. With the help of the diagnostic platform, all diagnostic centers, all inspection methods, and all inspection prices are covered in detail.*

DEPARTMENT OF PHARMACY. *Information about all pharmacies located in the territory of Uzbekistan will be posted. In it, the service of ordering and delivering the nearest pharmacy and the cheapest medicine will be launched.*

IN THE MEDICINE DEPARTMENT. *Information about all drugs is fully posted.*

Keywords: *MEDICINE , HEALTH, DISEASES, ARTICLES, USEFUL ADVICE, CLINICS, MEDICAL TECHNIQUE, NEWS, DIAGNOSTICS, PHARMACY.*

This platform covers several areas.

MEDICINE

HEALTH

DISEASES

ARTICLES

HELPFUL TIPS

CLINICS

MEDICAL TECHNIQUE

NEWS

DIAGNOSTICS

PHARMACY

DEPARTMENT OF MEDICINE

Medical department includes a) Scientific department, b) Documentation department.

All scientific works related to medicine are located in the scientific department. One scientific employee is attached to each scientific department.

The documentation department provides for the automation of all medical documents.

HEALTH, HELPFUL TIPS SECTION.

The Health and Fitness Tips section contains over 5,000 health tips and health tips, all science-based, copyrighted, and sourced.

DEPARTMENT OF DISEASES.

All diseases are presented by sections and placed according to the source used. The origin, symptoms, causes, treatment methods of all diseases are given in detail.

DEPARTMENT OF CLINICS.

Department of clinics includes a) Private, b) State institutions.

A separate mobile application is provided for the clinic department.

All information in the clinic section is placed in the following order.

Addresses of all institutions (private, state).

Specialists.

Working time.

Online admission.

Consultation prices.

Full information about 103 services is available.

MED TECHNIQUE, NEWS, DIAGNOSTIC CENTERS.

Information will be posted in stages in the Med Tech and News section.

The diagnostic section includes the following.

All diagnostic centers.

All inspection methods.

All inspection prices.

DEPARTMENT OF PHARMACY.

Special attention was paid to the pharmacy department. The pharmacy department includes

a) pharmacies b) drugs.

DEPARTMENT OF PHARMACY. Information about all pharmacies located in the territory of Uzbekistan will be posted. In it, the service of ordering and delivering the nearest pharmacy and the cheapest medicine will be launched.

IN THE MEDICINE DEPARTMENT. Information about all drugs is fully posted.

The Med1.uz site includes a number of domains and digitizes the entire medical field for easy and convenient access to users.

AptekaMed.uz domain, which is considered a pharmaceutical network, is active on the Med1.uz site .

The AptekaMed.uz site is one of the professional pharmaceutical web resource sources of Uzbekistan, covering a wide range of the pharmaceutical industry market.

The site provides relevant, verified, regularly updated information on the following categories:

Medicines and instructions for them;

Medical institutions of different profiles;

Manufacturers of medicines and medical equipment from Uzbekistan, the CIS and far abroad;

Wholesale companies;

Vacancies in the pharmaceutical industry and medicine.

A mobile application has been developed to provide addresses of all pharmacies throughout Uzbekistan, drug prices and find the nearest pharmacy.

Yandex service has been activated to show you the nearest pharmacy and the list of the cheapest medicines and to deliver the medicine you need without leaving your home . AptekaMed.uz is the most popular source of information on pharmaceuticals and medicine among all doctors and pharmacies in all regions of Uzbekistan who use this site to get medicines and many other information, as well as pharmacies and provides communication between users.

In addition, AptekaMed.uz unites well-known pharmaceutical organizations (distributors, wholesale firms, representative offices, manufacturers) and pharmacies throughout the republic.

PHARMACY MED CONCEPT

General concepts:

Popular drugs,

home page,

settings,

About Us,

location,

menus,

drug search,

notifications,

notice board,

2. Basic terms and concepts:

User(s) - any individual who uses Apteka Med to search for medicines and medical supplies from pharmacies in the Republic of Uzbekistan;

Search result - a page generated by the Apteka Med search system in response to a user's request to search for drugs and medical supplies;

The seller is a business entity (pharmacy) engaged in the retail sale of drugs and medical products in the Republic of Uzbekistan based on the relevant licenses;

Merchandise information - information about the seller's goods, as requested by the user, including, but not limited to: product name and description, price, seller's company name and trademark (if any), seller and addresses of its branches (if any), and contact information at Apteka Med;

3. Terms of use:

3.1 Popular drugs,

3.1.2 Show statistics of popular drugs,

3.1.3 The most sold drugs during a month,

3.1.4 Automating the process of viewing the list of best-selling drugs through Apteka Med mobile application and @Aptekamedbot.

3.1.5 4 Automate the list of active partners who sell the best-selling drugs through Apteka Med mobile application and @Aptekamedbot.

3.2 Homepage:

3.2.1 The home page of a mobile application contains an overview of the application.

3.3. Settings.

3.3.1 Profile settings.

3.3.1.1 Personal information, fish, contact information, telephone, e-mail address, gender information.

3.3.1.2 Security Settings.

3.3.1.3 FAQ.

3.4 About Us.

3.4.1 Contact Us.

3.4.1.1 Contact via e-mail address info@aptekamed.uz.

3.4.1.2 Communication using the Support Center.

3.4.1.3 Communication using the online chat support center.

3.4.2 Search for drugs.

3.4.2.1 Search for drugs through the website www.aptekamed.uz.

3.4.2.2 Searching for medicines via Telegram bot @aptekaMEDbot.

3.4.2.3 Searching for medicines using the mobile application version APTEKA MED.

3.5. Location determination.

3.5.1 Location determination First select the country Uzbekistan.

3.5.2 Location selection region selection.

3.5.3 Location selection district selection.

3.6 The menu is in the upper left corner under the positioning section.

3.6.1 Profile settings.

3.6.2 Drug search history.

3.6.3 List of favorite drugs.

3.6.4 Security System.

3.7 Search Engine.

3.7.1 All drugs are searchable.

3.7.2 System for filtering found results according to search results.

3.7.3 Add the nearest, cheapest, list, map and delivery service of search results.

3.8 Notices

3.8.1 Sending notifications about updates and changes to the Application.

3.9 Notice Board.

The materials submitted by the customers to the website (comments and other information about medicines) are placed on the basis of the document on the inclusion of these medicines in the State Register of Medicines and Medical Products of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Materials on drugs were published in an officially approved publication. All the information you need for your health on the Med1.uz site. Med1.uz will be the main domain. All domains will be part of Med1.uz. Med1.uz - Academy of Digitized Medicine and Health is transferred to the state register as an LLC under the name of the state register. All platforms will be rolled out in stages.

Med1.uz - Academy of Digitized Medicine and Health

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